

ACOUSTIC EMISSION STUDY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DAMAGE IN *GRP* AND *GRP* STRUCTURES

M. G. PHILLIPS and B. HARRIS

School of materials science, University of Bath, U.K.

Studies of the damage under tensile load incurred by test samples of various kinds of *grp* have been carried out with the aid of an acoustic emission monitoring system with amplitude distribution analysis. The same techniques have also been used in pressurisation tests on torispheric pressure vessel ends. It is shown that the structure of a *grp* laminate exerts a dominating influence on the *AE* patterns observed, and that direct correlations between microfailure events in the composite and the amplitude distributions of the acoustic emissions cannot be made. As a consequence the understanding of *AE* patterns from any given *grp* structure may only be possible if there is already a substantial background knowledge of the behaviour of similar structures under known conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Design methods for metallic structures have the backing of well-established proof-testing routines and non-destructive evaluation procedures, but for reinforced plastics the situation is far less satisfactory. Experience of *grp* in structural applications is limited and the effects of long term exposure to load and service environment are not known with certainty. Furthermore, our understanding of the microstructural mechanisms of damage in *grp* is far from complete. Reinforced plastics structures, especially those fabricated by hand lay-up from random mat reinforcement (*cbm*), frequently contain defects such as resin rich regions and voids. And because of the physical nature of composites at the microstructural level additional defects are readily created during service or even during proof loading sequences. As a consequence there is an urgent need to develop better *NDE* methods and other techniques for assessing the accumulation of damage in *grp* structures in order that more economical, but safe, structures may be built. Acoustic emission monitoring, a technique that has given useful results when applied to metallic structures, appears currently to be one of the more promising methods. However, the microstructural complexity of the composite material and diversity of types of material that are known, collectively, as '*grp*' make it difficult, if not impossible, to apply *AE* monitoring procedures that have worked satisfactorily for metals directly to composite materials. The fracture process in composites is much more complex, and local damage resulting from resin cracking, fibre failure, fibre/matrix debonding, or delamination for example, will usually be widely distributed. The acoustic responses of composites of different microstructural character will be quite different, and the emissions from a laboratory sample may be quite different from those from a large structure of the same material.

In our research program we are attempting to characterise the *AE* from a range of materials and structures in an effort to observe obvious distinguishing features that could form the basis of *NDE* or in-service assessment routines. The program is being carried out in collaboration with Professor S.S. Gill and his colleagues in the Department of Mechanical Engineering at U.M.I.S.T. whose own research concerns the evaluation of *grp* for pressure vessels and the internal pressurisation of large torispheric pressure vessel ends.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHODS

Two types of equipment are being used in this work. The principal analytical tool is an Acoustic Emission Technology Corp. 203 Amplitude Distribution system. This system is a multichannel analyser, monitoring the number of *AE* events as a function of time, load or pressure, and sorting the amplitudes of these events into 50 channels of 1.2 dB/channel with a range from 10 mV to 10 V. An FAC-500 PZT transducer is used with this system. The secondary monitoring system is a Dunegan (Endevco) 3000 series unit, coupled with an AETC RMS meter, which gives a record of the number of ring-down counts and the mean pulse height as a function of time, load etc. A D-140B transducer is used with this equipment, and the standard amplification is 80 dB. The effective signal threshold (at the transducer) is 100 μ V, compared with 20 μ V in the AETC system.

PRESSURE VESSEL MONITORING

The domed pressure vessel ends tested at U.M.I.S.T are about 1 metre in diameter. They are hand-laid up under production conditions by P.D. & E. of Warrington, from Crystic 491 A polyester resin (Scott Bader) with nine layers of 450 g/m² of Fibreglass chopped strand mat, to an overall glass content of about 26 wt. %. They are pressurised to failure according to a prescribed sequence of loading and unloading, incorporating time delays, the distortion of each vessel being monitored with strain gauges and displacement transducers. The AETC probe was sited near the pole of the vessel (fig.1) and during some tests the Dunegan (Endevco) transducer was located on the lower wall of the vessel near the retaining flange. The monitoring procedure was to plot the *AE* counts and events as a function of time during each loading and unloading phase of each cycle, periodically photographing the amplitude distributions on the AETC display. Fig.2 shows a smoothed series of

curves of *AE* events versus pressure obtained from the sixth in the series of U.M.I.S.T. vessels. Other vessels have given similar results. The curves show the events recorded in each cycle, the counter being reset after each unloading. *AE* activity first increases as the peak pressure is increased and relatively few events are observed on unloading. In several tests, maximum activity occurred in the penultimate cycle, as in fig.2, in which the peak pressure was about 63% of the final failure load, while activity in the final (failure) cycle was much lower.

A comparison of three continuous monitoring methods can be obtained from fig.3, which shows logarithmic plots of the numbers of events and ring-down counts during the third and fourth pressurisation cycles of the sixth U.M.I.S.T., vessel, together with *RMS* traces. Each of the three segments in each curve corresponds to a rapid loading phase followed by a 10 minute dwell. The ringdown total has been arbitrarily divided by 10, and it can be seen therefore that there are roughly ten ringdowns per event initially in cycle 3. This ratio falls slightly below 10 in the last two phases of the cycle and so remains until the last phase of the failure cycle when a preponderance of high amplitude events would be expected to raise its value. The records from the two monitoring locations are seen to be identical.

The *RMS* signal indicates that the greatest level of activity occurs during the rapid loading phase, as expected, while the mean level during the dwell is much lower. The increasing incidence of time-dependent damage at higher pressures is clearly indicated by the *RMS* record. In the third cycle, the bands of high activity are very narrow, whereas in the fourth cycle they are much wider as well as being lower on average. In the fifth (failure) cycle (not shown) the mean pulse height is still lower and the *RMS* bands are spread uniformly throughout the whole dwell period.

A typical set of amplitude distribution plots for a pressure vessel test (the ninth U.M.I.S.T.) is shown in fig.4. This shows how the shape of the log (cumulative) curve changes as the pressurisation level is raised, the display being cleared between load/reload sequences. At very low pressures the shape of the curve is typical of that for 120 kPa (7% of failure pressure), being concave downwards with the highest amplitude counts being at about 30 dB. Between 28% and 70% of failure pressure, the curve is straighter, with a mean slope of 1.3 and a maximum pulse amplitude of about 45 dB. The slope changes very little in this range, implying a high degree of stability. At 90% of failure (1600 kPa) there is evidence of a higher rate of counting of pulses from 6 to 24 dB, the curve becoming humped in this region. Only during the final loading to failure do we find a significant upward shift of the right hand part of the curve, indicating emission of high amplitude pulses as shown by the histogram of the same data. The shape of the histogram suggests a uniform distribution of amplitude, with no fine structure such as might be attributed to specific microfailure mechanisms.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION STUDIES OF COUPON TENSILE TESTS

During the tensile loading of test coupons of a variety of *grp* laminates, *AE* monitoring shows different patterns resulting from different structural characteristics of the composites. Fig.5 shows records of total ringdown counts as a function of stress during loading to failure of three types of laminate. These are glass/epoxy composites, two of which are 0/90 cross-ply materials — one with woven ($V_f = 0.47$) and one non-woven ($V_f = 0.67$) reinforcement — and the third being unidirectionally reinforced ($V_f = 0.67$). The total number of ringdown counts at failure varies widely with both V_f type and orientation of reinforcement, and it is clear that there is no simple, universal relationship between number of counts and stress or strain levels. It follows that there is equally no unique relationship between the integrated count in a fracture test and such materials properties as strength and modulus, but this is not unexpected when we consider the complex combination of microfailure events that must occur in different types of laminate. In the 0/90 non-woven laminate there is a high level of acoustic activity at relatively low strains, starting at strain levels of about 0.1%. The count rate rises to a peak at 0.7% and then declines to a minimum at about 1% strain before rising again in an exponential manner to failure (fig.6).

These emissions are clearly identified with cracking of the transverse plies, which is complete at strains of about 1%, the final spacing of the transverse cracks being roughly equal to the ply thickness (fig.7). This mechanism is peculiar to non-woven 0/90 laminates. It does not occur in woven-cloth laminates, as fig.5 shows, and it cannot occur in *osm* laminates although fibre/resin debonding at interfaces transverse to the applied stress — the same mechanism that initiates transverse ply failure in the non-woven laminates — must also contribute to the *AE* patterns of these other materials.

One of the purposes of amplitude analysis of *AE* signals is to try to establish direct relationships between the observed amplitudes and specific microfailure events. It is questionable, however, whether unique relationships can exist. At fibre failure, for example, different amounts of energy are released depending upon the extent to which the fibre has debonded from the resin prior to failure. A fibre aligned with the stress axis might debond over a distance of several millimetres before it breaks, whereas a fibre crossing a resin crack at an angle of more than about 40° will break with almost no debonding. The debonded fibre will therefore release several hundred times more energy at failure than the unbonded one. Similarly, fibre fracture resulting from exposure of *grp* to the conjoint action of stress and some aggressive environment — 'stress-corrosion cracking' — takes place with no debonding, cracks propagating smoothly from fibre to fibre, as shown in fig.8. When cracking of this kind occurs at low working stresses (about 10% of failure load) in high quality unidirectional (pultruded) rod many acoustic emissions occur, continuing with time at constant load, but very few of these emissions have amplitudes greater than about 30 dB above threshold, as illustrated in fig.9. The slope of the log-cumulative plot (the *b*-value) for such behaviour would therefore be extremely high, contrary to what has popularly been believed.

For comparison, fig.10 shows typical results of coupon tests from three types of *grp* tested under normal conditions; the woven and non-woven glass/epoxy composites already discussed, and some *osm*/polyester laminate ($V_f \approx 0.15$). The grouped plots refer to results obtained by loading a specimen to increasingly high load levels, the display being cleared before each new increment. The load levels are indicated as a fraction of the failure load, σ_f . The woven cloth laminate (tested parallel to one set of fibres) generates a relatively small number of events, all of low amplitude, and this clearly reflects the fact that the final damage zone in such laminates is localised, with relatively little debonding of fibres parallel with the stress axis. Even at failure the highest amplitude events are only about 30 dB above threshold. The mean slope of the log(cumulative) plot is of order 2.6 until the load exceeds 95% of the failure load. Only beyond this is there any sign of an upward tilt (lower *b*-value) in the higher amplitude region. The non-woven laminate is much noisier (as fig.5 showed) and at only 20% of failure events are monitored over the whole range. Little change in distribution occurs up to 50% of σ_f and this is reflected in the log(cumulative) plot, for which the mean *b*-value is 1.23. It is significant that whereas a large proportion of the microfailure events contributing to the total *AE* of the woven cloth composite must be fibre failures, it is certain that almost all of the emission from the non-woven composite at loads up to 50% σ_f would have been caused by transverse ply cracking. The *osm* laminate gives results quite different from those of the continuous fibre composites. Although the general trend is for the slope of the log(cumulative) curve to become smaller as the load increases, the curves are insufficiently uniform to permit assignment of *b*-values. On the other hand, the shape of the histogram for the final loading to failure does suggest that two quite distinct failure mechanisms could be identified, one with a mean event amplitude of about 15 dB and one at about 45 dB. These basic differences in *AE* characteristics of the three simple, conventional types of *grp* show clearly that simplistic attempts to interpret amplitude distributions in terms of composite structure and local failure processes are likely to be suspect.

DETAILED STUDY OF *AE* BEHAVIOUR OF POLYESTER/*osm* PLATE

In the light of these differences in acoustic emission behaviour between diverse composites, it was decided to concentrate attention on a single type of

material to discover whether significant changes were wrought in its *AE* pattern by the normal variations which might be encountered from sample to sample, or by different test conditions. To look at this in the opposite way, the object was to discover whether an acoustic emission 'signature' of the material showed through all these variations. The most clearcut result of this work was that defective samples, as defined by inferior breaking load, showed up very clearly by the different way in which their acoustic emission patterns develop at low loads.

The material chosen, because of its similarity to that used for the U.M.I.S.T. pressure vessels, was hand laid up to a nominal thickness 6 mm and comprised four layers of 450 g/m² chopped strand mat in Crystic 272 polyester resin. The glass content was approximately 27% w/w. Specimens of length 230 mm and uniform width 27 mm were used throughout, so that all strengths etc are expressed simply as loads in kilograms force.

A factorial design was adopted to encompass the following variables, and to discover their effects upon strength and acoustic emission output of the material:

1. Two levels of cure conditions :
Cure 1, 16 hours at 40°C.
Cure 2, 3 hours at 80°C.
2. Two levels of strain rate, as represented by crosshead speeds of 0.05 and 0.5 mm min⁻¹ in tests on samples of standard length.
3. Two levels of "orientation". Since all *as*m material is nominally isotropic, two directions of the sheet material were arbitrarily designated 0° and 90° directions.
4. Four load increments.

The large amounts of acoustic emission generated under some conditions cause the registers of the amplitude sorting equipment to overflow, with the result that interpretation of the remaining information is uncertain. It was decided therefore to record the *AE* amplitude distribution at load intervals of 200 kgf, and immediately clear the registers. If an overflow condition should occur it could be detected by reference to a record of the cumulative event count for that load increment.

The load increments chosen were 0-200, 200-400, 400-600 and 600-800 kgf. In most cases these stopped short of specimen fracture, which is accompanied by very large numbers and rates of acoustic emissions. Attention was therefore focussed on the predictive aspect of acoustic emission monitoring.

The bulk of the work to be reported here concerns tests in which samples were loaded continuously to failure. However, reference is made to 'stepped loading' tests in which the testing machine was stopped when the chosen load level had been reached, and a 'dwell' period of ten minutes passed before the next load increment. In these tests the *AE* amplitude distribution was recorded on arrival at the load level, and again at the end of the dwell period, with registers being cleared only at the end of dwell. The same crosshead speeds were used in continuous and stepped loading tests.

The overall plan of the experiment for one type of loading is illustrated in Table 1 which gives the breaking load of all samples tested in continuous loading.

TABLE 1

Pattern of experimental conditions, and breaking load (kgf) for continuous loading tests.

Cure Condition	Cure 1		Cure 2	
	0.05 mm/min	0.5 mm/min	0.05 mm/min	0.5 mm/min
"Orientation" 0°	1200	1120	450	855
	1180	1030	1040	960
90°	1110	1200	930	970
	1260	965	930	1000

RESULTS

1. BREAKING LOAD

It is immediately apparent from Table 1 that two specimens were very much weaker than the rest. Variance analysis of the strengths of the remaining samples shows no significant variation attributable to orientation or loading rate, but the reduction in strength caused by using Cure 2, i.e. from 1157 to 955 kgf is significant at the 1% confidence level.

The two weaker samples, identified as B1.06 and B2.01 are clearly from a different population, and they have been excluded from the overall assessment of acoustic emission behaviour which follows. In a later section they are compared with representatives of the main group of 14 remaining samples.

2. AE EVENT COUNT

In continuous loading tests the number of events recorded in a load increment increased exponentially with load level, as fig.11 shows. There were however differences, significant at the 1% confidence level, between Cure 1 and Cure 2, and between the two strain rates, so these factors are presented separately in fig.11C & E.

The unavoidable use of a logarithmic scale for event count tends to reduce the impact of these differences but the main effect of cure condition, fig.11C, is roughly to double the numbers of events recorded at each load increment on going from the low-temperature to the high-temperature treatment. This change accompanies a reduction in mean breaking load from 1157 to 955 kgf which represents unit loads of 420 kNm⁻¹ and 347 kNm⁻¹ for the two cases. These results are consistent with the earlier observation that in composites with non-woven reinforcement the bulk of acoustic emissions are associated with resin cracking. The higher degree of cure obtained in the higher temperature treatment reduces the strain to first fracture of the resin as expected.

Fig.11E shows that a tenfold increase in loading rate causes an increase approximately fourfold in the number of events per load increment. The true value of this ratio may be greater, since any spurious events or noise will be a larger proportion of the total at the slower rate, i.e. in a test of ten times longer duration. It must be supposed that the smaller number of events is recorded at the lower strain rate because the resin is able to relax viscoelastically in the available time. In fig.11F and D are presented comparisons between the build up of AE event count under identical conditions in 'good' and 'bad' testpieces, as defined by breaking load. Fig.11F refers to cure condition 1, and the higher testing rate. Although both test pieces withstood loads in excess of 800 kgf, it may be seen that at the lowest load level the event count for the weaker was double that of the stronger, and that this ratio increased progressively as load built up.

A much greater disparity, of order twenty times, existed at all load levels

between the samples illustrated in fig.11D which represents cure condition 2 tested at the slow rate. There is the suggestion of gross defects being present in one of these samples which broke when the load was increased beyond 400 kgf

The purpose of stepped loading tests is to discover whether the opportunity for relaxation during the dwell period modifies either the total number of *AE* events recorded, or their amplitude distributions. At the same time, the onset of creep and other time dependent phenomena can be detected, so that it may be possible to derive a criterion of internal damage similar to the "Felicity Ratio", but more conveniently measured.

At the time of writing only a few of these tests have been carried out. A comparison of 'good' and 'bad' specimens is shown in fig.11A and B. Presentation is different here from the previous tests. The open bars represent counts at the end of a load increment (or beginning of a dwell period) and the total length of the bar gives the event count at the end of the ten-minute dwell. It is necessary to read across figs.A and B to compare the samples. Both samples were high-temperature cured, and tested at the higher rate. It appears at first sight that in this case the main difference between the specimens was that the weaker one generated more counts on loading, in exactly the same way as for the continuous loading tests. However, the hatched portion of the bar is in effect a multiplier, so that the events recorded during the dwell are more numerous the higher the starting value. As the pressure-vessel tests have shown, the approach of failure can be signalled by an increase of *AE* activity during dwell periods, so further investigation of this point is in progress.

3. AMPLITUDE DISTRIBUTION ANALYSIS

To demonstrate the use of amplitude distribution analysis we present in figs.12, 13 and 14 results from the same pairs of testpieces, 'good' and 'bad' as previously discussed. Commencing at the bottom of each figure, successive histograms correspond to increasing load increments. The vertical scale of the histogram, representing number of events at a given amplitude level is in each case linear and identical in corresponding load increments but it should be noted that the scales are different at different load levels.

In the continuous loading tests on Cure 1 material (fig. 12) amplitude distribution appears to be exponential, with a progressive increase in the occurrence of higher amplitude events as the load level increases. When the two testpieces are compared, it is clear that the additional event count recorded for the weaker sample is mostly made up of events in the higher amplitude ranges.

There is a difference in character of the amplitude distributions from Cure 2 material under continuous loading (fig. 13) The histograms are bi-modal indicating as has been suggested above, that two principal micromechanisms of fracture may be operating. Once again there is the marked difference in high amplitude events between stronger and weaker samples.

In the stepped loading tests on Cure 2 material, fig.14, it appears that events recorded during dwell periods are quite uniformly distributed across the amplitude channels, as distinct from the exponential distribution found during loading. At the higher loads, this latter distribution appears to develop a second peak, rather as in fig. 13 .

DISCUSSION

In tests covering a wide range of *grp* materials and testing conditions, it has been discovered that there is a high degree of consistency in the acoustic emission behaviour of a good quality laminate, provided that test conditions and instrument settings are carefully reproduced. Against this background it is possible to distinguish at an early stage of loading between a defective and a sound sample of well characterised material. Materials with different layup patterns give different *AE* patterns, and in some simple cases where corroborative evidence can be obtained from microscopy, certain aspects of the *AE* pattern can be attributed to specific microfailure mechanism.

Amplitude distribution analysis is potentially a very powerful technique for the non-destructive examination of composites, but it appears to the authors

that the simpler techniques have very limited scope in this field because of the great number and variety of possible *AE* sources in a composite. To detect the presence of defects is not sufficient. It is necessary both to locate and identify *AE* sources which proclaim the presence of harmful defects.

The problems are considerable as has been discussed above. It seems improbable that a single specific microfailure event can ever be identified with an *AE* signal of a particular amplitude. One is therefore left with the alternative approach of examining all the acoustic emissions from a sample or structure and attempting to identify unique features by a statistical approach. In a single test such as those described in this paper, it is commonplace to count twenty thousand events, sometimes at rates approaching two thousand per second, which is the limit of existing hardware. This mass of data cannot be handled without a computerised acquisition system, which we are fortunate enough now to have installed at Bath. The next stage of our work is to develop analytical techniques for characterising the data, which will be done using a much larger computer to which we have access at the Science Research Council's Interactive Computing Facility.

Acoustic emission has in some quarters the reputation of a technique which has been a long time coming. In our view it has become worthy of consideration as an *NDI* method for large composite structures only since microprocessor-based systems became available. If these systems follow the downward trend in price set by other computer hardware, and at the same time, as they surely will, improve in sophistication to meet the complex requirements of composites testing, acoustic emission will shortly become that much needed practicable tool for quality control of *grp*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described in this paper is largely funded by the Polymer Engineering Directorate of S.R.C., and we are grateful for the Directorate's contribution to the organisation and development of our program. It is a pleasure also to acknowledge a fruitful collaboration with Professor S.S. Gill and his colleagues at U.M.I.S.T., and to recognise the substantial contributions to our work made by our own colleagues Mr. C. Arnold and Dr. F.J. Guild.

Fig. 1. Arrangement of AE probes during monitoring of U.M.I.S.T. pressure vessels.

Fig.2. Sequence of smoothed AE (events) versus pressure curves for the pressurisation of U.M.I.S.T. vessel no.6.

Fig.3. Comparison of three AE techniques used during the 3rd and 4th pressurisation cycles of UMIST vessel no.6. The total events recorded at the pole of the vessel varies in a manner almost identical with the total ring-down count from the probe on the side wall. The RMS trace registers the intensity of activity at the ring-down probe.

Fig.4. AE amplitude displays obtained during pressurisation of U.M.I.S.T. vessel no.9.

Fig.5. AE (ring-down) from three glass/epoxy laminates loaded to failure in tension. The ordinate relates AE to sample cross sectional area.

Fig.6. Load and AE as functions of tensile strain for samples of non-woven (cross-plyed) and woven cloth glass/epoxy laminates. The counter was operating in rate mode, so that the height of the AE curve at any point is the number of ring-downs per second.

Fig.7. Cracking of transverse plies in the non-woven laminate whose load versus strain curve is shown in the upper part of fig.6, after unloading from about 50% of the failure load. The ply thickness is about 0.6 mm.

Fig.8. Cracking in pultruded glass/epoxy rod after exposure to a surface strain level of the order of 10% of the failure load in the presence of hydrochloric acid (see fig.9).

Fig.9. AE occurring during exposure of pultruded glass/epoxy rod to stress in the presence of $2\frac{1}{2}$ N HCl. The surface of the rod was lightly abraded and polished prior to testing.

Fig.10 AE amplitude distributions from tensile tests on three types of grp. The left hand diagram in each case is the classical histogram showing number of events (linear) per amplitude channel, while the right hand diagrams (unscaled) show the cumulative distributions plotted logarithmically.

STEPPED LOADING TESTS - CURE 2

CONTINUOUS LOADING TESTS

Fig.11. Build up of AE event count with increasing load for several csm/poly-ester plate samples (see text for explanations).

Fig.12. Building up of AE event count with increasing load for several csm/polyester plate samples.

Cure 1 : loading rate 0.5 mm min^{-1} , continuous.

Fig.13. AE amplitude distributions, following identical load increments, for two nominally identical samples of csm/polyester plate. Note the difference in failure load, F_U .

Cure 2; loading rate 0.05 mm/min, continuous.

Fig.14. AE amplitude distributions following identical load increments, for two nominally identical csm/polyester plate samples. Note difference in failure load F_u .

Cure 2 : loading rate 0.5 mm min^{-1} , stepped.